

Semi Structured Interview Script

Introduction

Thank you for joining us today. We appreciate you volunteering your time to talk with us.

- My name is _____, and I am a researcher in the _____ department at _____ institution. I will be conducting the interview today.
- The purpose of this interview is to gather information about your experience in the software engineering field.

1 Recording audio

During the interview we will record the audio and video for internal purposes only. Our discussion will be recorded using Microsoft Teams. If you do not wish to have your video recorded, we will delete the video recording and only audio files will be kept for analysis. All digital files will be encrypted and stored on a password protected computer by the researcher.

2 Transcribing audio

- Your name will be removed from the transcript. You will have a coded number attached to your name, which only the study team members will know.
- The interview discussion will be transcribed using the audio obtained from this session.
- Before we start, I will share my screen with the consent form. Please take a minute to read it.
[walkthrough the main points]
 - Do you have any questions?
 - Do you agree to proceed with the interview?[fill out the consent log]

3 Semi-structured interview questions

Background:

1. Tell us a little bit about yourself:
 - a. What do you do?
 - b. What is your job title?
 - c. Company name?

Current Situation:

2. How would you describe your current role?

Pathway(s):

3. How did your career in Software Engineering begin?
 - a. Did you have a formal software engineering education?

- b. Could you describe your journey in software engineering?
- c. Was your education or training software engineering related?

Motivation(s):

- 4. What motivated you to build knowledge in software engineering
 - 4_1. Was there a specific moment, event or person that influenced this choice? (inflection point)
 - 4_2. Have your motivations changed as you progressed in your education?
- 5. What motivated you to pursue a career in software engineering?
 - a. Was there a specific moment, event or person that influenced this choice? (inflection point)
 - b. Have your motivations changed as you progressed in your career?

Challenges:

- 6. Could you describe any challenges that you have faced throughout your software engineering education?
 - a. How did you overcome these challenges if you did?
- 7. Could you describe any challenges that you have faced throughout your career?
 - a. How did you overcome these challenges if you did?

Next Steps:

- 8. How do you see your career evolving?

Thank you very much for taking the time to meet with us today. We really appreciate your time. That concludes the interview. Your responses will greatly benefit software engineering research. I will be stopping the recording at this time.

Snowballing:

- 9. Do you know of other people who might have had a different pathway into this field (i.e. self-taught, transitioned from another discipline)?
- 10. Do you know of other people who may be able to offer other perspectives and motivations?